

effected by using acetone dicarboxylic acid or its ester. For instance, by the action of nitrous acid on acetone dicarboxylic acid Pechmann and Wehsaig (*Ber.*, 1886, 19, 2465) obtained $\alpha\alpha'$ -disonitrosoacetone, $\text{HON}=\text{CH}-\text{CO}-\text{CH}=\text{NOH}$ (VI).

In the molecule of acetone, when one of the two methyl groups has reacted, further reaction generally does not take place at the second methyl group to produce an $\alpha\alpha'$ -product, but again at the first to produce $\alpha\alpha'$ product. Thus, when acetylacetone (VII) in the formation of which one of the two methyl groups of acetone has reacted, is further acetylated, the product formed is $\alpha\alpha'$ -diacetylacetone (VIII) (Nef, *Annalen*, 1893, 277, 71).

When, however, sodium derivative of acetone monoaxalic ester reacts with sodium ethylate and oxalic ester (Claisen, *Ber.*, 1891, 24, 116), or when oxalic ester (2 mols.) acts upon acetone (1 mol.) and sodium ethylate (2 mols.) in two instalments (Willstätter and Pummerer, *Ber.*, 1904, 37, 3734) the product formed is the disodium derivative of $\alpha\alpha'$ -acetone-dioxalic ester, $\text{EtO}_2\text{C}-\text{CO}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CO}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CO}-\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$ (IX)

With a view to studying the action of two molecules of formic ester on acetone, we added to sodium (1 atom) a mixture of the ester (1 mol.) and acetone (1 mol.) and then another atom of sodium and another mol. of the ester. We also worked by adding to sodium (2 atoms) a mixture of the ester (2 mols.) and acetone (1 mol.). The reaction was carried out at ice temperature and in ether as the solvent. In both the cases we obtained a disodium derivative which on acidification gave $\alpha\alpha'$ -diformylacetone, $\text{C}_4\text{H}_6\text{O}_3$ (X)

which is the simplest 1:3:5-triketone.

Diformylacetone (*bis*-hydroxymethylene acetone) was obtained in aqueous solution by Willstätter and Pummerer (*Ber.*, 1905, 38, 1470) by hydrolysing its *tris*-diethylacetal,

which in its turn was prepared from 1:4-pyrone and *ortho*formic ester. They, however, did not isolate the pure ketone from its aqueous solution and did not analyse it. They also have not described any of its functional derivatives except its green copper salt, $\text{CuC}_5\text{H}_4\text{O}_3$.

The compound isolated by us is a liquid and very soluble in water. Its composition has been proved from its analysis. It forms a semicarbazone and gives a violet coloration with ferric chloride. Like other 1:3:5-triketones it forms a non-chelate copper salt, $\text{CuC}_5\text{H}_4\text{O}_3$, the properties of which agree with those described by Willstätter and Pummerer (*loc. cit.*). On standing for some days it gradually turns into a brown solid

which we have not yet investigated. Simultaneously the intensity of its coloration with ferric chloride fades.

In the reaction described above an appreciable amount of monoformylacetone (XI) was formed, which in the hydroxymethylene form (XIa)

readily turned into its self-condensation product, 1:3:5-triacetylbenzene (XII) (Claisen and Styrol, *Ber.*, 1888, 21, 1145).

The latter being a solid could be separated from the liquid diformylacetone or its aqueous solution.

In an attempt to obtain diformylcyclohexanone the only product that was isolated proved to be the monoformyl derivative, hydroxymethylenecyclohexanone.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Diformylacetone Dicarboxylic Ester.—To pulverised sodium (4.6 g, 2 atoms) covered by dry ether and kept at ice temperature, was gradually added a mixture of ethyl formate (14.8 g, 2 mols.) and acetone dicarboxylic ester (20 g., 1 mol.). The reaction mixture was kept at 0° for 1 day and then at room temperature for 2 days. The disodium derivative formed was filtered at the pump and washed with ether; yield 26 g. It was dissolved in minimum quantity of cold water and the alkaline solution was extracted with ether, made slightly acid with acetic acid and again extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed and dried and the solvent removed. The residual liquid (10 g.) was fractionated and the crude diformyl derivative (b.p. 150°-175°) on further fractionation distilled at 174°-176°, yield 3.4 g. (Found C, 50.9; H, 5.4; C₁₁H₁₄O₇ requires C, 51.1, H, 5.4 per cent)

The compound readily forms a semicarbazone which on crystallisation from hot dilute alcohol melts at 192-93° (Found: C, 39.7; H, 5.5; N, 30.0. C₁₄H₂₀O₇N₂ requires C, 39.1; H, 5.3; N, 29.3 per cent).

It gives a violet colour with ferric chloride and turns blue litmus red. It is appreciably soluble in water. It forms, in almost theoretical amount, a green copper salt on shaking with aqueous solution of copper acetate. The purified copper salt after drying in an oven at 100° was analysed. (Found: Cu, 20.0. C₁₁H₁₂O₇Cu requires Cu, 19.8 per cent).

On decomposition with cold dilute hydrochloric acid the copper salt regenerated the diformyl derivative.

αα'-Diformylacetone.—To pulverised sodium (6 g., 2 atoms), covered by dry ether and kept at ice temperature, was gradually added during the course of 45 minutes a mixture of acetone (7.5 g., 1 mol.) and ethyl formate (18.5 g., 2 mols.). The reaction initially was vigorous and care was taken not to allow the temperature to go above 0°. The mixture was kept at this temperature for one day with occasional shaking and then was allowed to remain at room temperature for 2 days with shaking as before. The disodium derivative formed was filtered at the pump and washed with ether. The dry salt weighed 27.5 g.

The derivative was dissolved in minimum quantity of ice-cold water and extracted with ether. The aqueous alkaline solution was made slightly acid with acetic acid and left to stand for sometime. Crystals of 1.3.5-triacetylbenzene, produced by self-condensation of monoformylacetone formed in the reaction, began to separate. These were identified from their melting point and the melting point of the semicarbazone. After 2 hours the liquid was filtered from the crystals and extracted five times with chloroform. After washing, drying and removal of the solvent the crude diformylacetone weighed 9 g. On repeated fractionation further amount of the solvent was removed and a liquid boiling between 98° and 101° (3 g.) was collected. (Found: C, 52.5; H, 5.6. C₈H₆O₂ requires C, 52.6; H, 5.26 per cent).

It is a thin colorless liquid, very soluble in water and gives acid reaction. It colours ferric chloride violet. It forms a semicarbazone which on crystallisation from hot dilute alcohol melts at 160°. (Found: C, 33.9; H, 4.9; N, 43.8. C₈H₁₂O₂N₂ requires C, 33.6; H, 5.2; N, 44.2 per cent).

On adding it to a cold concentrated solution of copper acetate the solution became green but no copper salt separated. After standing for some hours a green crystalline copper salt slowly deposited. The salt is appreciably soluble in water. It was washed with minimum amount of cold water and after drying at 100° it was analysed. (Found: Cu, 36.1. C₈H₄O₂Cu requires Cu, 36.3 per cent). The salt gives a nearly colorless solution in glacial acetic acid. When an aqueous solution of the disodium salt, made just acid with acetic acid, is poured into excess of cold concentrated solution of copper acetate, the copper salt of *αα'*-diformylacetone is obtained as a green crystalline precipitate on rubbing. 28 g. of the sodium salt gave copper salt which on drying weighed 12 g. This on crystallisation from hot water was found on analysis to be identical with the copper salt prepared directly from the ketone.

In this preparation much of the diformylacetone remained dissolved in the aqueous medium and could not be completely extracted by the solvent. It was isolated in the form of copper salt which proved on analysis to be identical with the copper salt described above. Its semicarbazone could also be prepared from the aqueous solution.